

**Antimicrobial activity of nanoconjugated glycopeptide antibiotics and their effect on
Staphylococcus aureus biofilm**

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Figure 2

Panel A

Time (min)	CTRL		IONPs		VANCO		NP-VANCO		TEICO		NP-TEICO	
	OD600 nm	Dev std										
0	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000
60	0,125	0,000	0,125	0,000	0,125	0,000	0,125	0,000	0,125	0,000	0,125	0,000
120	0,342	0,002	0,301	0,047	0,177	0,003	0,087	0,024	0,209	0,004	0,091	0,004
180	0,980	0,007	0,353	0,013	0,182	0,001	0,100	0,016	0,223	0,006	0,007	0,015
240	1,635	0,002	0,929	0,002	0,165	0,004	0,096	0,020	0,216	0,004	0,000	0,022
300	1,913	0,011	1,202	0,004	0,155	0,003	0,086	0,017	0,207	0,002	0,000	0,037

Panel B

	CFU	Dev std
VANCO	1,433e+06	1,876e+05
NP-VANCO	4,000e+06	8,796e+05
TEICO	1,000e+05	0,000
NP-TEICO	0,000	0,000
CTRL	1,088e+09	5,394e+07
IONPs	7,880e+08	5,182e+07

Panel C

Time (min)	CTRL		IONPs		VANCO		NP-VANCO		TEICO		NP-TEICO	
	OD600 nm	Dev std										
0	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000	0,100	0,000
60	0,089	0,000	0,089	0,000	0,089	0,000	0,089	0,000	0,089	0,000	0,089	0,000
120	0,152	0,002	0,304	0,022	0,140	0,000	0,011	0,026	0,108	0,006	0,023	0,010
180	0,280	0,013	0,346	0,041	0,129	0,003	0,005	0,018	0,108	0,005	0,016	0,011
240	0,478	0,015	0,450	0,057	0,121	0,002	0,000	0,017	0,103	0,001	0,104	0,018
300	0,707	0,020	0,568	0,052	0,120	0,002	0,000	0,031	0,098	0,003	0,141	0,017

Panel D

	CFU	Dev std
VANCO	0,000	0,000
NP-VANCO	4,000e+05	0,000
TEICO	6,000e+05	0,000
NP-TEICO	7,333e+05	76376
CTRL	3,120e+07	2,475e+06

IONPs	7,880e+08	5,182e+07
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Figure 3

Panel A

	OD590 nm	Dev std	CFU/well	Dev std
CTRL	11,263	3,196	1,500e+06	7,071e+05
TEICO	4,319	1,906	4500,000	4979,000
NP-TEICO	5,240	1,385	1050,000	1343,500

Panel B

	CFU/mL	Dev std
CTRL	1,950e+05	35355
TEICO	366,670	378,590
NP-TEICO	150,000	70,711

Panel C

	OD590 nm	Dev std	CFU/well	Dev std
CTRL	21,315	1,098	5,250e+08	1,768e+08
TEICO	1,140	0,401	1,210e+05	1,400e+05
NP-TEICO	0,860	0,385	7,885e+05	1,006e+06

Panel D

	CFU/mL	Dev std
CTRL	1,285e+08	1,294e+08
TEICO	550,000	494,970
NP-TEICO	1600,000	565,690

Panel E

	OD590 nm	Dev std	CFU/well	Dev std
CTRL	13,545	1,645	3,600e+08	1,414e+07
TEICO	2,4943	0,646	1,367e+05	75056,000
NP-TEICO	5,159	1,416	2,379e+06	4,003e+06

Panel F

	CFU/mL	Dev std
CTRL	1,500e+08	1,414e+07
TEICO	19667,000	15948,000
NP-TEICO	3,000e+05	4,187e+05

Panel G

	OD590 nm	Dev std	CFU/well	Dev std
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CTRL	11,263	3,196	1,500e+06	7,071e+05
VANCO	2,784	1,664	633,330	923,760
NP-VANCO	9,915	2,532	1,467e+06	6,351e+05

Panel H

	CFU/mL	Dev std
CTRL	1,950e+05	35355,000
VANCO	100,000	0,000
NP-VANCO	5833,300	5795,100

Panel I

	OD590 nm	Dev std	CFU/well	Dev std
CTRL	21,315	1,098	5,250e+08	1,768e+08
VANCO	1,568	1,818	2,600e+07	3,677e+07
NP-VANCO	2,086	2,642	3,550e+07	1,485e+07

Panel J

	CFU/mL	Dev std
CTRL	1,285e+08	1,294e+08
VANCO	2,550e+05	3,323e+05
NP-VANCO	2,240e+07	2,348e+07

Panel K

	OD590 nm	Dev std	CFU/well	Dev std
CTRL	13,545	1,645	3,600e+08	1,414e+07
VANCO	4,275	1,624	1,420e+05	1,669e+05
NP-VANCO	4,262	2,602	2,000e+05	98995,000

Panel L

	CFU/mL	Dev std
CTRL	1,500e+08	1,414e+07
VANCO	32000,000	25456,000
NP-VANCO	1,750e+05	1,485e+05

Figure 4

Panel C

	OD590 nm	Dev std
CTRL	22,590	2,500
TEICO	15,250	1,170
IONPs	23,720	1,700
NP-TEICO	13,560	2,200

Figure 5**Panel A**

Time (hours)	IONPs		VANCO		NP-VANCO		TEICO		NP-TEICO	
	Cell viability (%)	Dev std								
0	82,000	3,000	100,000	2,000	112,000	2,000	91,444	0,500	91,578	2,500
24	82,500	5,000	103,000	3,000	109,000	1,500	99,485	0,500	95,241	2,000
48	86,000	7,000	104,000	1,000	102,000	0,500	95,821	1,000	86,929	1,000
72	85,000	12,000	96,000	3,000	87,000	2,000	97,005	2,000	69,004	2,000
96	80,000	8,000	94,000	2,500	93,000	2,000	105,100	6,000	66,677	2,400

Panel B

Time (hours)	IONPs		VANCO		NP-VANCO		TEICO		NP-TEICO	
	Cell viability (%)	Dev std								
0	38,000	3,000	113,000	1,000	96,000	2,000	98,962	1,000	59,810	3,000
24	42,000	14,000	111,000	0,500	92,000	1,000	107,700	0,500	60,730	2,000
48	39,000	12,000	100,000	1,000	82,000	2,000	100,830	1,000	43,052	3,000
72	39,500	10,000	83,000	1,000	77,000	4,000	96,004	0,500	50,938	5,000
96	45,000	2,000	91,000	2,000	74,000	4,000	96,184	1,000	98,581	3,500